

HEALTH RELATED LIFESTYLE: IT'S EFFECT TO THE PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the effect of health related lifestyle to personality development of junior high school students in Manuel S. Enverga Memorial School of Arts and Trades, Mauban for the school year 2020-2021. Specifically, this research sought to answer the respondents' level of practices as to the following health related lifestyle: health habits, eating habits and health care and preventive measure. What is the perception of the respondents to their personality development in terms of the following components: physical, emotional, mental, and social? What is the respondents' level of physical fitness in terms of the following components: cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, flexibility, muscular endurance? Is there significant relationship between respondents' Health Related Lifestyle and personality development and physical fitness? This research has 75 respondents, 47% are male and 53% are female. A survey questionnaire and Physical fitness test were the main instrument used in gathering the data from the respondents. The researcher used an online survey in which 60 learners were in the form of messenger and video call. Through video call, the researcher explained and showed how to do the 4 physical fitness tests and through it, the researcher explained each survey question in tagalog form so that the respondents could better understand what the sentences mean and what to answer. Upon completing the 75 respondents, the researcher also used the face to face method in the remaining 15 respondents which associated with following the health protocol, since not all respondents have the ability to answer using online. Conducting face to face is addressed with great care to the researcher and the respondents. A survey questionnaire was constructed by the researcher and submitted to her adviser for comments and suggestions on the layout and statement structures. Then, the researcher sought help from the experts for proper guidance, constructions, and suggestions. The initial draft of the questionnaire tried out to 15 junior high school students of Manuel S. Enverga Memorial School of Arts and Trades Mauban, Quezon. The favorable findings have shown confirmation that the questionnaire was valid. All data and instruments used were validated and checked by concerned school authorities for accuracy and validity. Frequency percentage, standard deviation, mean was used in the description table to determine the profile of the respondents. Pearson Product Moment of Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the significant relationship between Independent and Dependent variables. Findings revealed as to the level of practices in terms of health habits has a mean 3.77 agree, eating habits 3.71 agree and health care and preventive measure 3.83 agree. As to perception of the respondents in terms of physical has a mean of 4.02 agree, emotional 4.03 agree, mental 4.14 agree and social 4.13 agree. As to the result of the test, majority of the respondents performed "fair" in cardiovascular endurance and muscular strength. In flexibility and muscular endurance, the respondents performed "excellent." Thus it can be concluded that there is significant relationship between respondents' Health Related Lifestyle and personality development and physical fitness. Based on the findings Learners are encouraged to spend more time on physical exercise to lessen the stress, tension in

studying and to maintain a healthy body and lifestyle. At this time of pandemic, follow health protocol and always consult to doctor for medical consultation whenever something is wrong. Families, school and communities should continue sharing health wellness resources, for the children to remain updated and aware of any changes in wellness standards.

Keywords: health related lifestyle, personality development, health habits, physical fitness